

Improving Nursing Staff Confidence in Pediatric Code Blue Events

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Background

- Cardiac arrests on general pediatric units can be a challenge as they are considered low-frequency and high-risk situations
- Use of Rapid Response Teams has improved outcomes by reducing code blue events
- Nurses expressed decreased confidence in dealing with a code blue and a need for additional training to enhance skills
- The purpose of this project was to implement a skills training day for to improve nurses' confidence when performing skills needed in a code blue

Methods

Provide skills practice for nursing staff on four identified skills utilized in code blue:

- Crash cart contents review
- Medication administration review
- Review of fluid bolus using "push/pull" method
- Use of defibrillator

Theoretical Framework

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory

- Self-efficacy is the ability to handle situations and how it influences behavior
- Influenced by cognitive factors, motivation, affective factors and decision making

Intervention

- Nurses working on a 32-bed general pediatric medical surgical unit
- Staff pre-scheduled to attend one of two skills sessions
- Staff rotated every 50 minutes to each of the four stations to practice skills
 - Instructors provided information to both groups informing of project and optional survey participation
- PALS instructors were used as skills station instructors
 - Same instructors for both classes
- Utilized Schwarzer General Self-Efficacy Scale
 - Additional questions developed related to skills

Results

- 68 Registered Nurses participated in the intervention
- 67 Registered Nurses completed the pre/post surveys
- Greater confidence reported on post-intervention survey in all four skill areas
- 92% found intervention very helpful in providing an overview of code blue events
- 91% found intervention very helpful in providing opportunities to practice code blue skills

Comparison of Pre- and Post-Intervention Scores on Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale

General Self-Efficacy Scale	Pre-Intervention	Post-Intervention	p-value
	Median (IQR)	Median (IQR)	
Total Score	30.0 (3.0)	32.0 (5.0)	0.02

Distribution of Responses to the Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale

Discussion

- Nurses were provided the opportunity to practice skills not often utilized
- Utilize staff input to determine future education results in a positive learning experience for the nurses
- Scheduling sessions during non-work hours is an important consideration for projects such as this one
- 8 nurses had a decrease in self-efficacy
 - May be related to perceived self-confidence prior to intervention

Future Implications

- Determine appropriate frequency of intervention provision for staff
- Follow up/debrief with staff after code blue events to evaluate performance and utilization of skills
- Reinforce learned information
- Develop booster sessions or videos posted to unit SharePoint site to sustain staff knowledge
- Follow up to measure performance during actual or simulated events

